

THE MOTIVATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract: This article seeks to examine the significance of motivation in the teaching and learning process for both students and teachers. It explores how meaningful learning occurs through the interaction between teachers who stimulate their classes with knowledge and students who are motivated to explore, investigate, and acquire new skills within the educational environment. The qualitative research is based on theoretical content and utilizes a deductive-inductive method, drawing from journals, bibliographies, and analytical descriptions. The outcome includes insights into student motivation, as well as techniques and methodological strategies to help students achieve their learning objectives.

Keywords: *education, types of motivation, teaching-learning process, theory, students, developing skills.*

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является анализ мотивации и значения педагогического процесса обучения для учащихся и учителя, а также того, как взаимосвязь значимое обучение между учителем, который передает знания, генерирующей стимулировать свои классы и учеников, которые способны исследовать, исследовать, приобретать новые навыки посредством мотивации, обеспечиваемой образовательной средой. Качественное исследование описывает теоретическое содержание, руководствуясь дедуктивно-индуктивным методом, на который ссылаются журналы, библиографии и аналитические описания. В результате у студентов появляется мотивация, методы и методологические стратегии достижения поставленных целей.

Ключевые слова: *образование, виды мотивации, учебно-учебный процесс, теория, учащиеся, развитие навыков.*

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola talabalar va o'qituvchi uchun o'quv jarayonidagi motivatsiya va ahamiyatini va ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. bilim beruvchi o'qituvchi o'rtasida mazmunli o'rganish o'z sinflarini va o'quvchilarni kashf qilish, tekshirish, ta'lim muhiti tomonidan taqdim etilgan motivatsiya orqali yangi ko'nikmalarni o'rganish. Sifatli tadqiqot jurnallar, bibliografiyalar va analitik tavsiflardan olingan deduktiv induktiv usulga asoslangan nazariy mazmuni tavsiflaydi. Buning natijasida talabalarda motivatsiya, texnika va o'z maqsadlariga erishish uchun uslubiy strategiyalar.

Kalit so‘zlar: ta’lim, motivatsiya turlari, o‘qish va o‘rganish jarayoni, nazariya, bilim va ko‘nikmalar.

At present, the educational environment is changing. In different institutions, they are taking a turn around the new models of educational centers that are being updated every year to improve the teaching-learning process for students so that they are professionals capable of undertaking for life, teachers as a primary element, are facilitators of new study strategies and motivate showing interest to students, the importance of developing skills, aspirations, interests and ideals in education. common distinction made in the literature is between extrinsic and intrinsic forms of motivation. Intrinsic motivation is the act of doing an activity purely for the joy of doing it, and it is frankly very rare in school and work contexts. Extrinsic motivation, or the use of external rewards or punishments to encourage student work completion, is generally painted in education as the enemy of good instruction. This is true to a certain extent because, as learning is comparable to exploration, the use of rewards or punishments tends to outline a boundary around how much a student should explore.

However, there are actually many different forms of extrinsic motivation, and not all are equally likely to lead students down a path of apathy and dissociation from the joy of learning. For example, one extrinsically motivated student may work hard in school because they fear failure and the anger of their parents. Another may study hard because they see the value of the content in helping them work toward their dream of becoming a doctor. Neither student in these examples is intrinsically motivated – their goals lie outside the simple enjoyment of the activity. However, the second student is likely to be more independent and self-guided in their learning because they recognise the value of these extrinsic rewards. This form of motivation is much more sustainable because it does not require constant threats or prizes from teachers or parents. There is also some research to suggest that extrinsic motivation can lead to intrinsic motivation, in the sense that students may embark on a task for reasons associated with extrinsic motivation but become intrinsically motivated through the process of engaging with the task and learning to value it.

Achievement Goal Theory argues that all motivation can be linked to one’s orientation towards a goal. According to this theory, there are two forms of goal: performance goals and mastery goals. Performance goals are based on satisfying one’s ego by appearing smart in front of one’s peers or on achieving a sense of superiority. Mastery goals are, as they sound, motivated by a desire to fully master a skill or concept. Students with mastery goals will finish a project when they are proud of it rather than when it meets the minimum requirements. Even after they turn in the assignment to be assessed, they may continue to reflect on it and make refinements. Mastery goals largely align with intrinsic motivation in the former theory. Some researchers in education have broken the concept of Achievement Goal Theory down further, borrowing the idea of approach and avoidant behavior from psychology. As the name suggests, students with

approach performance goals actively seek to outperform others while those with avoidant performance goals actively work to avoid being seen as inferior. While less studied, approach and avoidant orientations also apply to mastery goals as well.

This article implemented qualitative research because the theoretical peculiarities of motivation and the teaching-learning process were described; In addition, the research is bibliographic, evidenced in the development of the work, based on an extensive bibliographic search in books, internet magazines and other materials that were analyzed. Deductive-inductive and analytical-descriptive methods were used. The bibliographic, because thematic contents are supported by citations extracted from texts and electronic sections that served as references that demonstrate the research perspective; deductive is used to describe the themes that started from the general to the particular; inductive because contents of facts that started from the particular to the general were analyzed; Analytical-descriptive, because a detailed narration of various contents was made with critical contributions and relevant purposes to explain reality.

The types of motivation in learning according to comments that there are different people who have goals and objectives that exist, the extrinsic motivation that refers to not always going to be motivated to carry out some activity, sometimes interest is diminished, that is, you need another person to encourage you to continue, on the other hand, the intrinsic motivation, this is to make agility for pleasure and allows you to do activities and be an autonomous and competent person; the positive motivation is the one that is always with the desire for gratification is driven by itself, the negative motivation is born from the failure of the person who appears if they do not reach their achievement; The basic motivation is the one that focuses on commitment, the daily motivation is the one that is presented and short-term goals are met. Figure 1 shows the types of motivation in learning.

The types of motivation used in learning with more frequencies are; intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation, which depends on them being in functions of being positive or negative when motivating. You should always motivate with interests when teaching activities that develop progress in the attitude of the human being.

Also, Morón (2011), states that intrinsic motivation is necessary for people, as well as for teachers and students because three experiences are born:

- a) Improve what you have learned and the desire to compete with your own knowledge.
- b) Performing activities for his own interest elevates his emotional ego and rewards himself for the proposed goal.
- c) Nature is part of your motivation, makes you get out of the routine and changes the way you develop the skills you propose

The importance of motivation mentions that the teacher is a character that plays an important role in establishing a relationship of trust to motivate in the construction of knowledge and learning, for example, be on the lookout to guide in the methodological, didactic processes, awakening the level of development that they can expose. The brain causes the human being to generate a behavior of changes in behavior explains that the

brain creates brain processes that start from previous knowledge, therefore it receives a motivational stimulus through external information, which indirectly causes him to produce an involuntary self-esteem when developing some skill in his learning is an elementary part of life. At present it is sometimes difficult to apply motivational theories in the classroom since they are forgotten by those involved in education, affirms that school learning has its own knowledge and that it depends on subjects such as (mathematics, science, etc.) to be motivated within the context. In learning, experiences that flow within the classroom regarding motivation with emotional self-regulation is considered so that emotions are spontaneous as well as the ability to improve intrinsic motivation in the student, the teacher is incorporated in leveling the methodological proposals to improve enrichment for meaningful learning. At the world level, the famous digital era has been formed that students are updated more and more every day, that students do not motivate them if they do not perform with some kind of technology or technological programs then in their research analyzes that One way to motivate the aulic classes requires that digital tools such as (mobile phones, laptop, or programs as an instrument or work material) In the new digital era, the paradigms take a turn of change to conceive meaningful learning, for therefore where the processes do not limit the teacher that the students activate basic cognitive processes and conservation of information for new learning situations, the teacher being a mediator of motivation for the student. A teacher who has knowledge about motivation and learning must have various theories of motivation, is to increase their research and application of it to students to improve or highlight the learning they acquire during the educational process that increases attention and Interest in his career. According to Alemán when investigating the teachers of the different motivational theories, it does not imply precisely to nurture the cases but to sustain the academic rhythm of an institution in learning.

In conclusion, motivational methods in education should be enhanced to benefit student learning, fostering values and enthusiasm for the skills they acquire. Teachers should offer positive motivation to students both within and outside the learning environment, enhancing productivity and reinforcing values in their teaching.

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